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Faith, Reason and the University Reflections on a Recent Address of the Pope

Julian Saldanha S J

Professor of Theology, St. Pius X College, Mumbai

Abstract: In this article the author gives a creative and critical appreciation of the Papal Address at the University of Regensburg on “Faith, Reason and the University”. After studying the various reactions to the talks, especially from the Muslims, the author respectfully shares some of his reflections on the Address of the Pope, and deals with the issue of secularization. This analysis and the reflections are offered with frankness, honesty and respect, as part of the “dialogue of cultures” and religions, to which Benedict XVI invited us, in the last paragraph of his address at the University of Regensburg and in his subsequent apology, and for which he has since been repeatedly calling. May it be read in this spirit

Keywords: *Fides et Ratio*, *Nostra Aetate*, secularization, Regensburg Speech, faith, reason, university, Islam.

1. The Reactions

I refer here to the Address which Pope Benedict XVI delivered at the University of Regensburg on 12 September, 2006. He had been professor and vice-rector here from 1969 to 1971. I use the Vatican translation of the address (entitled “Faith, Reason and the University”), which was available on the internet (www.zenit.org). We know that addresses of this type are meant for a worldwide audience, especially since the Vatican immediately put it on its website in German and Italian and little later in English.¹ His comments on the prophet Mohammed and on Islam, in the form of a quotation from a 14th century Byzantine emperor, immediately ignited furious protests among Muslims worldwide. Several Muslims termed

his remarks blasphemous, some wanted him removed from office, and some Muslim clerics even called for his death, which is the penalty for such blasphemy in some Muslim countries.² Some saw a sinister “axis” between the U.S. President George Bush and the pope, with a view to some sort of crusade against Muslims. But in retaliation, no disparaging comment was made by Muslims about Jesus. In fact, to the best of my knowledge no such comments are found in all Muslim history, whereas very insulting comments have been made by Christians about Mohammed in the course of Church history.³ The situation did not improve much, after the Vatican spokesperson and then the Secretary of State (Cardinal Tarcisio Bertone), issued a statement saying that the pope was “deeply sorry for the reactions in some countries to a few passages” of his address. Note that this statement does not express regret for the inflammatory quotation. Matters seemed to have calmed down only after the pope personally declared that the words he uttered in the form of a quotation “do not in any way express my personal thought”.

In India, Church personnel, who either commented in the newspapers or appeared on TV, tried their best to defend the pope, by stating that the remarks were taken out of context and that the quotation was of the emperor, not of the pope. They affirmed that the pope and the Church have great respect for Islam. Hence I attempt in this article to analyse the pope’s speech for what it really says. My effort is to try to understand the pope’s controversial comments *in their context*.

2. The Address

The theme of the address is that faith and reason belong together and hence should not be separated. He began by recalling his years in the university, where theologians inquired into the reasonableness of faith and sought to correlate faith with reason as a whole. The rest of his speech is devoted to indicating the harmful effects of separating reason from faith. He selects two examples of this: Islam (as a religion) and today’s Europe (as a continent). It would have been better if he had chosen the Christian religion, with which he and his audience was more familiar, rather than Islam, in order to illustrate his point. I shall return to this below.

2.1 Islam

In connection with Islam, he refers to a dialogue (edited by professor Khoury) which took place between “the erudite Byzantine emperor Manuel II Paleologus and an educated Persian on the subject of Christianity and Islam, and the truth of both”. Although the emperor made one point which “itself is rather marginal to the dialogue itself”, nevertheless the pope selects it “as the starting point for my reflections on this issue”. This shows the importance he attaches to the point made by the emperor and how much it is part of his own thinking. Before quoting the emperor, the pope makes his own exegesis of the Koran concerning holy war. He holds that in the early period, “when Mohammed was still powerless and under threat” he could afford to say: ‘There is no compulsion in religion’ (Sura 2:256). But at a later stage he developed instructions concerning holy war. He then returns to the emperor, “with the central question on the relationship between religion and violence in general, in these words: *‘Show me just what Mohammed brought that was new, and there you will find things only evil and inhuman, such as his command to spread by the sword the faith he preached’*” (emphasis added). One wonders why, out of hundreds of possible quotations, especially about violence in the Christian tradition, the pope has chosen this particular one? Does it not show his purpose to reinforce the point made in the quotation of the emperor? This old quotation responds to the deep disquiet of his audience in Europe, over what they have come to dub as ‘Islamic’ terrorism. The pope does not express disagreement with this comment. In fact the context indicates that the emperor’s comment is also his own opinion. For immediately after this quotation he relates the emperor’s supporting explanation as to why spreading the faith through violence is something unreasonable, because violence is incompatible with the nature of God and of the soul; and not to act in accordance with reason is contrary to God’s nature. In contrast, for Muslim teaching, God is so absolutely transcendent that he is not bound by any of our categories, even of rationality. (This would presumably explain Islam’s endorsement of violence, according to him, to spread religion). As an example of this point of view the pope picks up a reference which professor Khoury makes to Ibn Hazn who apparently

tried to stress the transcendence of God by saying that God is not bound even by his own word and could even ask us to practise idolatry. The pope adds that this position of Ibn Hazn “might even lead to the image of a capricious God”. When the pope refers to a similar position of Duns Scotus (‘voluntarism’) he takes care to balance it with the ‘intellectualism’ of Augustine and Thomas Aquinas. No similar attempt is made by the pope to understand or balance the view of Ibn Hazn.

All this seems to be of a piece with some of the teachings he gave in 2000 as Prefect of the Congregation for the Doctrine of the Faith, in the Declaration “Dominus Iesus”; it was also signed by his then Secretary Tarcisio Bertone. Some passages there depreciate or discount other religions, which may not be very conducive to that inter-religious dialogue for which the pope has been calling after the recent furore over his remarks. The other religions are described as merely “the human treasury of wisdom and religious aspiration” (No. 7; see also: nos. 8, 21, 22).

2.2 Some Observations and Reflections

The view expressed in the pope’s quotation, underscored above, is patently incorrect, lacking in sensitivity and respect. We know how Christian exegetes of the inspired word of God in the Old Testament struggle to explain how God could call his people to wars which were sometimes not only defensive but also cruelly offensive: as for example the conquest and occupation of the land of Canaan (“you must utterly destroy them ... show them no mercy,” Dt 7.2); likewise the slaying of kings Sihon and Og was followed by the extermination of men, women and children (Dt 2.34; 3.6). The concept of “jihad” is much more complex than is made out in the quotation which the pope chose; the primary meaning of jihad is to battle one’s own evil inclinations and sins; the concept of defensive war arose at a later stage (See: Bowker and Eliade). Catholic spokespersons should not have fought shy of expressing this immediately, especially since it does not involve a point of Catholic faith. We know that in a much more important matter concerning Catholic morals, namely the encyclical “*Humanae Vitae*” of Paul VI, several bishops’ conferences in Europe almost immediately

qualified and modified the teaching in that encyclical, through pastoral letters. The bishops' conferences of Asia, if at all they commented, should have been more forthright in expressing themselves in the present case. This is confirmed by the fact that the pope himself later tried to distance himself from what he had quoted. It is the duty of the local churches to give honest and frank feedback to the centre. If this has not been happening, it is in large measure due to the gradual centralization which has been taking place in the Church and which peaked during the last 25 years, to a degree never before seen in the history of the Church. Not many have realized this.

In Islam an insult to the prophet Mohammed is considered equivalent to blasphemy. Likewise we saw a lot of protests from Christians recently, upon the release of the film on "The Da Vinci Code". Some dubbed the film as blasphemous and one Catholic, a former Municipal Corporator of Mumbai, even announced a large monetary reward for anyone who would bring before him Dan Brown (author of the book) dead or alive. The Christian leadership in Mumbai issued no press statement distancing itself from this statement. Fortunately the Muslim reaction to the pope's comments was peaceful, barring a few stray incidents of violence. It is some extremist and terrorist fringe groups who sought to make capital of the pope's remarks to further their cause.

A quicker apology on the part of the pope, such as the one he finally made, would have helped to calm the atmosphere much earlier. Here one wonders why the Pontifical Council for Inter-Religious Dialogue, instituted under another name in 1964 by Paul VI, was recently amalgamated by the present pope with the Pontifical Council for Culture. The head of the former Council was made a Nuncio elsewhere. This Council could have vetted all speeches or documents of the pope dealing with other religions; on occasion the Federation of Asian Bishops' Conferences (FABC) should also be consulted. This brings up another point. The centre of gravity of the Church has shifted to the southern hemisphere (south of Europe and North America), where the majority of Christians are found and the Church is flourishing. Is this sufficiently reflected in the thinking and attitudes in the administrative centre of the Church? This is not a question of

merely increasing the membership of the Roman Curia with personnel from the 'South', but of reflecting the thinking of the local churches here. Perhaps then here in Asia we will feel better understood at the centre regarding the approach to evangelisation and other religions adopted by the FABC.

The pope apologized ("the words do not in any way express my personal thoughts") for his insulting remarks, but we know from the context of his address, that they did indeed express his views at least at that time. Nevertheless we may presume that his apology was not merely meant to stem the storm of protests, but that he has sincerely changed his view of the prophet Mohammed and of Islam. He will now need to tell us what he appreciates about the prophet Mohammed and about Islam. That is the approach which Vatican II adopted in "Nostra Aetate": After detailing common elements in Islam and Christianity, the Council pleads: "Although in the course of the centuries many quarrels and hostilities have arisen between Christians and Muslims, this most sacred Synod urges all to forget the past and to strive sincerely for mutual understanding" (No. 3). This is wise guidance from a General Council of the Church!

In the dialogue of religions, self-criticism is the best form of criticism. At least before making any critique of another religion, the pope could have cited many examples of savage violence practised during the course of Church history, with sanction from the highest authorities in the Church, including popes: the crusades, the inquisition, the use of torture, the execution of heretics and 'witches', the military orders; the practice of slavery until the Church gave in to the strong anti-slavery wave sweeping through Europe and the Americas in the 19th century; the denial of religious freedom by Pius IX as contained in the "Syllabus" of errors (1864). Threats and force were used on a massive scale by Christian rulers to bring the peoples of northern and eastern Europe to the Christian faith. Thus in his "Capitulatio" (A.D. 785) for Saxons, Charlemagne ordered the death penalty for refusal to receive baptism and for participation in non-Christian sacrifices. The conquest and occupation of South America by the Iberian powers in the 15th century was accompanied with the subjugation and destruction of entire cultures. The point is that the few clergymen or ecclesiastical

authorities, who spoke out against the violent measures of the Christian kings, were exceptional. A reference to these matters, rather than to Islam, would have gone down better as a preface to his point that violence is something unreasonable, incompatible with the nature of God and of the soul.

The pope seems to present the ‘intellectualism’ of Sts. Augustine and Thomas Aquinas as examples of the synthesis between the Greek spirit and the Christian spirit which should not be sundered: otherwise one would probably see the type of violence unleashed which the pope sees in Islam. Still, Augustine who was at first opposed to the use of coercive measures against the Donatists, like confiscation of property, later acquiesced. He felt that such persons who were unconcerned to inquire about Catholic truth, when pressurized by imperial decrees which threatened earthly loss, became Catholics and were glad to be so (*CSEL*, 34:461-463). Thomas Aquinas was of the opinion that heretics and all apostates “should be submitted even to bodily compulsion”. And Christians may “wage war with unbelievers, not indeed for the purpose of forcing them to believe ... but in order to prevent them from hindering the faith of Christ”. In general the rites of non-Christians (exclusive of Jews) must in no wise be tolerated by a Christian ruler (*S.T.*, II-IIae, q. 10, a. 8 & 10). No wonder non-Christian temples were destroyed on a large scale in Goa and all over the other European colonies in the 16th century.

In suggesting that Islam separates reason from faith, the pope has ignored a strong rational trend in Islam, which one sees already in the *Mu'tazila*, a theological school of thought, which flourished particularly from the 8th-9th centuries. Embracing Greek rationalist modes of argumentation, the *Mu'talizites* advocated the use of reason in finding a middle way between unbelief and naïve fideism. In modern times we have Muhammad Abdul engaged in similar pursuits. *Ibn Sina* (980-1037), known as Avicenna, was a Spanish Islamic Neoplatonist philosopher, theologian and scientist. He mastered Aristotle's metaphysics, convinced that human reason could ultimately lead to the attainment of truth. He articulated the truth of Islam according to Aristotelian logic and Greek metaphysics. His work, translated into Latin, had great influence on Thomas Aquinas and others in the Middle Ages. His philosophy was banned for a

while in the 13th century, but again permitted by Pope Gregory IX in 1231. *Abul Walid ibn Rushd* (1128-1198), known as Averroes, was an Arab philosopher of Spain who wrote a commentary on Aristotle. Some of his doctrines were neo-Platonist in origin. He aimed at harmonizing the Koran with philosophy and logic. It was a time of great cultural flowering in the Muslim world, with universities opened in Baghdad, Cairo, Tunis, etc. (Bowker; Eliade; Maqsood). Muslim scholars have developed a whole science of interpretation of the Koran.

2.3 Secularization

In the second part of his speech the pope is probably at his best, as he makes a welcome and ringing criticism of that approach to reality which “excludes the question of God, making it appear an unscientific or pre-scientific question”. As a result: “it is man himself who ends up being reduced, for the specifically human questions about our origin and destiny, the questions raised by religion and ethics, then have no place within the purview of collective reason as defined by ‘science’ and must thus be relegated to the realm of the subjective.” Consequently, “ethics and religion lose their power to create a community and become a completely personal matter”. The realm of reason must not be limited only to the empirically verifiable: “A reason which is deaf to the divine and which relegates religion into the realm of subcultures is incapable of entering into the dialogue of cultures.” The pope is aware that this criticism is applicable chiefly and primarily to the *Western world*, where “it is widely held that only positivistic reason and the forms of philosophy based on it are universally valid”. The West has failed to reflect on the questions which underlie its rationality. This would presumably include the question of why there is a “rational structure of matter” and why reason is reasonable? He concludes his argumentation: “For philosophy and, albeit in a different way, for theology, listening to the great experiences and insights of the religious traditions of humanity, and those of the Christian faith in particular, is a source of knowledge, and to ignore it would be an unacceptable restriction of our listening and responding.” No doubt, the world religions elsewhere would applaud these remarks. However, Catholic

theologians and editors of theological journals in India will mull over the irony of the pope's remarks, in the light of the atmosphere of fear which has today spread in theological circles.

One last point needs to be made, since it has special implications for the Asian churches. The pope's enthusiastic espousal of the rationality of Greek philosophy leads him to make a criticism of what "is often said nowadays that the synthesis with Hellenism achieved in the early Church was a preliminary inculturation which ought not to be binding on other cultures. The latter are said to have the right to return to the simple message of the New Testament prior to that inculturation, in order to inculturate it anew in their own particular milieux." These words supposedly are not meant to cancel out what his immediate predecessor wrote in the encyclical "Fides et Ratio: on the relationship between faith and reason" (1998, nos. 71-72); although this relationship forms the central theme of the pope's address, one searches in vain for any reference to this encyclical. John Paul II conceded that Christianity first encountered Greek philosophy, but added: "this does not mean at all that other approaches are precluded". On the contrary, "no one culture can ever become the criterion of judgment, much less the ultimate criterion of truth with regard to God's Revelation ... as if in engaging a culture the Gospel would seek to strip it of its native riches and force it to adopt forms which are alien to it." Already in 1975 pope Paul VI encouraged local churches to "translate the treasure of faith into the *legitimate variety of expressions of the profession of faith, of prayer and worship, of Christian life and conduct...*"⁴ Returning to "Fides et Ratio": John Paul II notes "a great truth: faith's encounter with different cultures has created something new". This leads the pope to outline the challenge facing us today: "as the Gospel gradually comes into contact with cultural worlds which once lay beyond Christian influence, there are new tasks of inculturation, which mean that our generation faces problems not unlike those faced by the Church in the first centuries." Here in India we warmly welcomed the fact, that in this context "my thoughts turn immediately to the lands of the East, so rich in religious and philosophical traditions of great antiquity. Among these lands, India has a special place." He is aware of the spiritual impulse and metaphysical systems which have powered the Indian religious tradition for millennia.

Consequently: "In India particularly, it is the duty of Christians now to draw from this rich heritage the elements compatible with their faith, in order to enrich Christian thought." The Asian churches surely have no intention of jettisoning the definitions of Christian faith as spelled out, with the help of Greek philosophy, in the early General Councils of the Church, but only of "creating something new", as John Paul II desired. We therefore expect that the Roman centre will understand the difficulty of our task, respect the freedom required for it, encourage and accompany us with constructive criticism and sympathetic understanding of what we are trying to say and do, regarding our approach to local cultures and religions.

The above analysis, observations and reflections are offered with frankness, honesty and respect, as part of the "dialogue of cultures" and religions, to which Benedict XVI invited us, in the last paragraph of his address at the university of Regensburg and in his subsequent apology, and for which he has since been repeatedly calling. May it be read in this spirit!

Notes

1. See the site www.vatican.va, accessed in October 2006.
2. An Italian nun was shot dead in Mogadishu, Somalia; this was most probably connected with the pope's remarks.
3. Grand-nephew of St Francis Xavier, Jerome Xavier's view was widely held at the time: he plainly told the Moghul Emperor Jehangir (ca. 1610) that Mohammed was in hell.
4. "Evangelii Nuntiandi", on evangelization in the modern world: n. 64; emphasis added.

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